

PHOST

“Physics of Oscillating Stars”

3 - 7 sept 2018, Banyuls-sur-mer (France)

What physics
can we learn from
oscillating stars ?

*This conference honours the life work
of Professor Hiromoto Shibahashi
(Tokyo University)*

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

PHOST

Physics of Oscillating Stars

WHAT PHYSICS CAN WE LEARN FROM OSCILLATING STARS?

A conference in honour of Professor Hiromoto Shibahashi.

Most of what we know of the universe comes from studying stars. From the birth and evolution of galaxies to the nature of planets, obtaining reliable results needs precise knowledge of the stellar outer parameters, as well as their internal structure and evolution. Until recently, this information only came from the observations and analysis of stellar light, by either spectroscopy or photometry. From these observations, we could derive the atmospheric temperature and pressure, the surface gravity, the magnetic field and the surface abundances of the chemical elements, by using model atmospheres. It was possible to measure the radius of nearby stars by using interferometry and we had access to surface rotation and activity from the study of spectral lines. However, the stellar internal structure could only be derived through evolutionary models.

The advent of helioseismology, in the 1970s, and asteroseismology, twenty years later, represented a revolution for stellar studies. The detection and analysis of stellar oscillation modes led to direct insight of the deep layers of the Sun and the stars. This gave access to their internal structure, depth of the convection zones, internal temperature, pressure and density, internal rotation, and more. Asteroseismology provided tools to distinguish hydrogen shell-burning from helium core burning red giant stars, as well as the evolution of their rotating cores. It also yielded precise values of the radii, masses, and ages of exoplanet-host stars, needed for a good determination of the parameters of the planets and a good characterization of their internal structure. Now, asteroseismic masses and ages for red giants, coupled to GAIA positions and space velocities, are fundamental to galactic archeology.

The study of the internal structure of the stars was initiated at the beginning of the 20th century by Sir A.S. Eddington and collaborators. The equations needed to describe self-gravitating spheres were solved several decades later with the help of the first computers. This enabled one to build approximate stellar models, with no rotation, no magnetic fields, no mass loss, no internal motions other than dynamical convection. The stellar medium was introduced as a unique gas, with an average molecular mass and average opacity. These models were then considered as “standard”. Later on, the precise constraints brought by helioseismology and asteroseismology led stellar physicists to improve these models considerably by adding a number of “non-standard” effects.

Studying and improving stellar physics is important for a better understanding of the stars themselves and their environment. Furthermore, stars represent laboratory sites for physical processes that cannot be tested experimentally on Earth. They help understanding basic physics, such as nuclear physics, particle physics, statistical physics, hydrodynamics, magnetic processes, atomic physics and opacities, and more. High performance computer networks presently available allow numerical simulations, which help to understand these physical processes. They are used in symbiosis with the most recent observations of stellar oscillations, for a better understanding of stellar internal structure and evolution, from pre-main-sequence T Tauri stars to the end states of White Dwarfs.

This conference honours the work of Professor Hiromoto Shibahashi, who devoted most of his scientific life to the study of oscillating stars. He was one of the co-authors of a textbook, "Nonradial Oscillations of Stars", published in the 1970s when the field of asteroseismology was in its infancy and had yet to be named. Over more than 40 years, Hiromoto Shibahashi has been in the forefront of both theory and observation of many related topics. This conference will celebrate his contributions by discussing how the latest research in the oscillations of stars is advancing our understanding of the physics of stars, as well as informing diverse fields from galactic archaeology to habitable exoplanets.

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PROGRAM

SUNDAY 2 nd SEPT.		
18:00	Registration and Icebreaker	
MONDAY SEPT. 3		
08:30	Registration	
09:00	Introductory address and opening of the meeting	
09:20	Tributes to Hiromoto Shibahashi (D. Gough, A. Noels, D. Kurtz)	
SESSION 1 : PHYSICS OF STELLAR PULSATIONS		
10:05	Current problems in stellar pulsation theory)	M.A. Dupret (R)
10:30	Tea/Coffee break	
11:00	Rotation effects on stellar pulsations	R.M. Ouazzani (R)
11:25	Oscillations of rapidly rotating stars: asymptotic theory	F. Lignières (R)
11:50	Effects of convection on stellar oscillations	J. Schou
12:10	Poster presentation 1	
12:35	Lunch break	
14:30	R-mode oscillations ubiquitous in stars	H.Saio
14:50	Mode classification in fast-rotating stars using a machine learning algorithm	G. Mirouh
SESSION 2 : METHODS OF ASTEROSEISMOLOGY AND SELECTED OBJECTS		
15:10	The Sun: the benchmark star for asteroseismology of solar-like pulsating stars	R. Garcia (R)
15:35	Solar-like pulsations across the HR diagram	O. Benomar (R)
16:00	Asymptotic solar g modes: How we measured the rapid core rotation	E. Fossat
16:20	Gravity modes with Kepler data: the gift that keeps on giving	T. Bedding
16:40	Coffee break and POSTERS SESSION	
TUESDAY SEPT. 4		
SESSION 2 : METHODS OF ASTEROSEISMOLOGY AND SELECTED OBJECTS		
08:30	Registration	
09:00	Super-Nyquist asteroseismology	H. Shibahashi (R)
09:25	Impact of magnetic fields on asteroseismology	S.T. Loi (R)
09:50	Can high angular degree non-radial pulsations be observed in roAp stars?	G. Mathys
10:10	RR Lyrae and Blazhko effect	Z. Kollath (R)
10:30	Tea/Coffee break	
11:00	First-overtone RR Lyrae stars - analysis of the Galactic bulge sample	H. Netzel
11:20	Seismology of subgiants and red giants: a powerful tool for stellar physics	S. Deheuvels (R)
11:45	Red Giant Asteroseismology in the Gaia Era	M. Pinsonneault
12:05	New pulsation physics from unusual red giant stars?	D. Stello
12:25	Lunch break	
14:30	Discontinuities in the core of red giant stars: effect on the mixed-mode pattern and how to measure it	M. Vrad
14:50	Asymptotic view of oscillations of red giant stars	M. Takata
15:15	Oscillation properties of High Luminosity Red Giants	J. Montalbán
15:40	The contribution of asteroseismology to a better understanding of helium core burning sdB stars	S. Charpinet (R)
16:00	PB8783 - a trailblazer for hot subdwarf asteroseismology in globular clusters	V. Van Grootel
16:20	Oscillation mode variability in pulsating hot B subdwarfs and white dwarfs	W. Zong
16:40	Tea/Coffee break and POSTERS SESSION	

WEDNESDAY SEPT. 5		
09:00	Stellar Autopsies from White Dwarf Pulsations	J.J. Hermes (R)
09:25	Driving Pulsation Modes in Hot DA White Dwarfs	G. Fontaine
09:50	The mystery of GW Vir instability strip in the light of new observations of PG 1159 stars	P. Sowicka
10:10	Non-luminous sources of cooling in pulsating white dwarfs	A. Kim
10:30	Tea/Coffee break	
SESSION 3 : STELLAR PHYSICS : MODELLING AND THEORY		
11:00	Current problems in stellar evolution	G. Buldgen (R)
11:25	Coupling interior and atmospheric models	H.G. Ludwig (R)
11:50	Understanding mixing processes through asteroseismology	V. Antoci (R)
12:15	Poster presentation 2	
12:35	Lunch break	
Afternoon	Excursions	
THURSDAY SEPT. 6		
SESSION 3 : STELLAR PHYSICS : MODELLING AND THEORY		
09:00	Constraints on convection and overshoot	C. Lovekin (R)
09:25	Calibration of the mixing length of the MLT and FST models using 3D hydrodynamical models	T. Sonoi
09:45	Anisotropic shear-driven turbulent transport in stellar radiative zones	S. Mathis
10:05	What have we learnt about B-type stars from their pulsations?	J. Daszynska-Daskiewicz (R)
10:30	Tea/Coffee break	
11:00	On the photometric detection of internal gravity waves in massive stars.	D. Bowman
11:20	Atomic diffusion in G and F type stars and its impact on the asteroseismic determinations of stellar parameters	M. Deal (R)
11:45	Opacity Calculations for Stellar Astrophysics	J-C Pain (R)
12:10	The effect of atomic diffusion on gravity modes of young stars with a convective core	J. Mombarg
12:30	Lunch break	
14:30	Pulsating Stars in Binaries	S. Murphy (R)
14:55	Post-common-envelope binary stars: Radiative levitation and blue large-amplitude pulsators	C. Byrne
15:15	Tidal Asteroseismology of Heartbeat Binary Stars	Z. Guo
15:35	Damping rates and frequency corrections of Kepler LEGACY stars	G. Houdek
16:00	Slowing the Spins of Stellar Cores	J. Fuller
16:20	Tea/Coffee break and POSTERS SESSION	
FRIDAY SEPT. 7		
SESSION 4 : TRANSDISCIPLINARITY : IMPORTANCE OF PRECISE STELLAR KNOWLEDGE		
09:00	On-going ground-based and space projects and perspectives	W.J. Chaplin (R)
09:25	Synergy between asteroseismology and exoplanet science: an outlook	T. Campante (R)
09:50	Planets and p-mode oscillations of a K-giant, HD 102103	A. Wolszczan
10:10	Asteroseismology and galactic archeology	A. Miglio (R)
10:35	Tea/Coffee Break	
11:05	Dark Matter Constraints from the Sun and Stars	I. Lopes (R)
11:30	Concluding remarks	
12:30	End of meeting/ Lunch break	

ORAL CONTRIBUTIONS

Session 1

PHYSICS OF STELLAR PULSATIONS

Current problems in stellar pulsation theory

Marc-Antoine Dupret^{*†1}

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Abstract

The last decade lead to major progress in asteroseismology and stellar physics with the advent of space missions. Thanks to the richness and precision of current oscillation spectra, sophisticated seismic probing techniques allow us now to pinpoint the limits of our current models of stellar structure and evolution. However, the accuracy of the seismic diagnosis depends on the accuracy of the pulsation models. In solar-like oscillations, the main source of inaccuracy comes from the near-surface layers where the oscillations are non-adiabatic and strongly coupled with turbulent convection. Some pulsating stars rotate fast and this must be accurately taken into account in the modelling of their pulsations. In others, the magnetic field, dynamic tides, ... could affect their pulsations. I propose an overview of these stellar evolution and pulsation problems as an introduction to the conference.

*Speaker

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Rotation effects on stellar pulsations

Rhita-Maria Ouazzani^{*†1}

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Abstract

Rapid stellar rotation introduces a number of phenomena that considerably complicate the modelling of stars and the interpretation of their pulsations. On the one hand, centrifugal acceleration reduces local gravity, mimicking a lower mass, and distorts the propagation cavity of pulsation modes. On the other hand, rotation induces dynamical processes such as meridional circulation, shear and baroclinic instabilities, and modifies the dynamics of pulsation modes. In this review, I will report on the effect of rotation on stellar oscillations, in light of the progress achieved thanks to space photometry.

*Speaker

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Oscillations of rapidly rotating stars : asymptotic theory

François Lignières*†¹

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Abstract

The short wavelength asymptotic analysis of acoustic and gravito-inertial waves allows for an understanding of stellar oscillation modes that in turn can be used to interpret seismic data. Here we review ray based asymptotic analysis of stellar acoustic and gravito-inertial modes in rotating stars, showing that it provides a physical classification of the modes as well as insight into the organization of the frequency spectrum, including the occurrence and origin of frequency regular spacings.

*Speaker

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Effects of convection on stellar oscillations

Jesper Schou^{*†1}

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Abstract

Some of the most significant problems in the understanding of stellar oscillations are believed to be related to the interaction of the modes with the near surface convection. One way these effects manifests themselves is through the so-called surface term, which requires the use of ad-hoc corrections in the analysis of the frequencies. Another way is through the presence of apparently non-physical center to limb effects in solar observation, leading to systematic errors in the determination of e.g. the solar meridional flow. Here I will briefly describe these problems, review some recent results and discuss what can be done in the future to address them.

*Speaker

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R-mode oscillations ubiquitous in stars

Hideeyuki Saio^{*†1}

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Abstract

R-mode oscillations are normal modes of global Rossby waves. They are generated by the Coriolis force acting on non-rotational horizontal motions, which should occur commonly by surface spots, non-synchronous tidal forces, mass-loss/accretion, and etc. Therefore, r-mode oscillations should be ubiquitous. Although motions are almost toroidal which causes no temperature perturbations, Coriolis forces generate horizontal compressions and hence temperature perturbations. Thus, r modes are visible even by photometric observations. The precise photometry by the Kepler satellite revealed the presence of r modes in many stars. I will talk about the signatures of r modes in various type stars.

*Speaker

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Mode classification in fast-rotating stars using convolutional neural networks

Giovanni Mirouh^{*†}, George Angelou², and Daniel Reese³

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Abstract

Delta Scuti stars are fast rotators whose spectra are very difficult to interpret: indeed, rotational effects scramble the oscillation spectrum so that we can no longer use single spherical harmonics to identify the modes. Theoretical work suggests that modes in fast-rotating stars can be split in various categories based on their geometry. The large separation of one of these categories is expected to scale with the mean density of the star, paving the way to ensemble asteroseismology of delta Scuti stars. We compute the oscillation spectra of fully-consistent two-dimensional modes of fast-rotating stars. We train a 2D convolutional neural network to classify automatically the modes in the theorized categories to bring out the expected patterns. I will discuss the obtained regularities, how they correlate with stellar fundamental parameters, and the comparison with observed stars.

*Speaker

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Session 2

METHODS OF ASTEROSEISMOLOGY AND SELECTED OBJECTS

The Sun: The benchmark star for asteroseismology of solar-like pulsating stars

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Abstract

The term "asteroseismology" was introduced by Christensen-Dalsgaard (1984) referring to the extension of the helio-seismic analyses to determine the structure and dynamics of the Sun to other stars and to provide a better test of the theory of stellar structure and evolution. In this talk I will review the latest advances in the Sun-as-a-star seismic analysis performed from ground-based networks as well as from space. In particular, I will review the evolution of the solar seismic properties with the magnetic activity cycle thanks to a long database of 40 years of seismic monitoring from ground and 22 years from space. These results will be discussed in the larger context of stellar evolution by comparing the Sun with other solar twins, analogs and the rest of the already observed main-sequence solar-like pulsating stars. It will be shown how the Sun's properties have been used as a reference or a benchmark to these asteroseismic studies.

*Speaker

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Solar-like pulsations across the HR diagram

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Abstract

By detecting nearly 20000 solar-like pulsators, the space missions CoRoT and Kepler have tremendously enhanced our understanding of low-mass stars. The asteroseismic data collected by those space missions allowed us to determine precisely radii, masses and ages of stars, enabling us to observe the evolution of stars with exquisite details. Asteroseismology also provided us an insight on the core of Red Giants, revealed rotation profiles and helped to constrain the exoplanets fundamental characteristics such as the mass, radius, orbit and habitability. This talk will review some of the major advancements in asteroseismology enabled by CoRoT and Kepler, with a particular focus on main sequence stars.

*Speaker

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Asymptotic solar g modes: How we measured the rapid core rotation

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Abstract

Solar g modes have been hunted for decades, as they have the potential of providing the core structure and rotation parameters. Being evanescent in the convective zone, they have never been convincingly detected at the surface. We have used a different approach, using the p modes as a tool for an investigation that can be compared to the medical ultra-sound imaging. A first challenge was to identify a p-mode parameter that would efficiently focus on the deepest layers, and that could be measured in a not too long time. The p-mode large separation gave access to a broad range of asymptotic g-mode frequencies. These are not expected to oscillate with large physical amplitudes, but they are many and their asymptotic properties permit an unambiguous statistical detection. After understanding that our "instrument" was located inside the sun, we have now in hand extremely precise values of the g-modes rotation rate and of the parameter P_0 .

*Speaker

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Gravity modes with Kepler data: the gift that keeps on giving

Tim Bedding*^{1,2}, Gang Li^{1,2}, Tanda Li^{1,2}, Yaguang Li^{1,3}, Simon Murphy^{1,2}, Timothy Van Reeth^{1,2}, Vichi Antoci², Rhita Ouazzani⁴, and Emily Kerrison¹

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Abstract

We have studied g modes using 4-year Kepler data. On the main sequence we find gamma Dor stars. About 20 rotate slowly, with doublets or triplets that allow measurement of the internal rotation profile. About 450 gamma Dor stars are rotating more rapidly, so that the prograde and retrograde modes are well-separated into long sequences of overtones. Their period spacings vary roughly linearly with period, but with irregularities caused by sharp gradients in chemical composition. Many stars also show Rossby modes. In subgiants, the g modes are not directly observable but they couple with the p modes to create avoided crossings. We compared the frequencies of the avoided crossings in dozens of *Kepler* subgiants with theory, which gives a reliable way to determine masses and ages (with application to TESS). Finally, red giants of intermediate-mass, which lack a degenerate core, display g modes whose period spacing gives a very good estimate of mass.

*Speaker

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Super-Nyquist asteroseismology

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Abstract

Photometric observations from space missions have provided us excellently uninterrupted data taken over long timespans with ultra-high precision and made it possible for us to investigate seismically the deep layers of stars.

Due to a telemetry limit, however, the sampling cadence of photometry is restricted, as in the case of the Long Cadence mode of the Kepler mission. Many stars are oscillating with shorter periods than this sampling (30 min), and consequently the Nyquist aliases of oscillations trouble in data analysis.

I will briefly review Super-Nyquist asteroseismology by the original Kepler mission, and then propose a new technique for future missions to overcome the problem of Nyquist aliases. The method only has to introduce modulation to the sampling program in advance. I will demonstrate that suitable combinations of the modulation frequency and amplitude allow us to identify the oscillation frequencies correctly.

*Speaker

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Impact of magnetic fields on asteroseismology

Shyeh Tjing Loi^{*†1} and John Papaloizou¹

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Abstract

Asteroseismology provides information not just about the material properties of a star, but also its symmetries. For a star that is sufficiently symmetric, its oscillation spectrum is regular. Strong magnetic fields alter wave propagation and break the spherical symmetry, potentially destroying this regularity. The consequences of these processes for the existence and properties of global modes are still not thoroughly understood. In this talk, I present results of investigations into the interactions of gravity waves with strong magnetic fields, using a combination of Hamiltonian ray tracing, analytical techniques, and numerical simulations. We uncover a rich variety of behaviours, including a transition to chaotic dynamics, when the field strength exceeds a certain threshold. Furthermore, we find evidence for a "trapping phenomenon" that may be relevant to the damping of g-modes in stars containing a strong core field.

*Speaker

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Can high angular degree non-radial pulsations be observed in roAp stars?

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Abstract

In the presence of a magnetic field, stellar spectral lines may appear systematically broader in one circular polarisation than in the opposite one. This rotational crossover effect, which is observed in some Ap stars, results from a correlation between the rotational Doppler shift and the different Zeeman shifts of the circularly polarised components.

Crossover of non-rotational origin has been detected in a number of roAp stars as well as in some noAp stars. The most plausible interpretation is that it is induced by the pulsational velocity gradients across the photospheric layer. Pulsational crossover is expected to be detectable even in the case of high angular degree pulsation modes, contrary to luminosity variations. Thus, it may open a new window into unexplored physics in roAp stars.

We present preliminary results of numerical simulations aimed at evaluating the magnitude of pulsational crossover and its observability.

*Speaker

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RR Lyrae and Blazhko effect

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Abstract

Since the discovery of the amplitude modulation of RR Lyrae stars by Sergey Blazhko in 1907, there have been countable tries to explain this behaviour. Studies linked the process behind the amplitude modulation to different effects, sometimes unphysical mechanisms. Here we present that the pulsation dynamics itself, without any added machinery, can lead to modulation of the amplitude with a similar fashion as the observations. The key is the interaction of the fundamental mode with the 9th (strange) mode, as predicted earlier. However, only the outer layers of the star play an essential role in the interplay of these modes, which makes hard to model the pulsation. This fact illuminates the lack of successful modelling in the past. On the other hand, the surface behaviour reveals some of the previously unexplained observational results. The complex dynamics of RR Lyrae pulsation solves some old problems but opens further questions.

*Speaker

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First-overtone RR Lyrae stars - analysis of the Galactic bulge sample

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Abstract

Thanks to the Optical Gravitational Lensing Experiment we know more than 11000 first-overtone RR Lyrae stars (RRc) in the Galactic bulge. Based on this numerous and homogeneous sample, we detected and analyzed stars with interesting phenomena: with non-radial modes and other additional signals, and with the Blazhko effect. We detected non-radial modes forming period ratio around 0.61 with the first overtone in a few hundred stars which gives the possibility to verify the model explaining this form of pulsation. In a few dozens of RRc stars we also found additional long-period signal forming period ratio around 0.68 with the first overtone. We discuss incidence rates and properties of stars showing these modes and of stars showing the Blazhko effect.

*Speaker

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Seismology of subgiants and red giants: a powerful tool for stellar physics

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Abstract

Thanks to the detection and precise characterization of non-radial oscillations in about 20,000 subgiants and red giants by space missions CoRoT and Kepler, these objects have become powerful tools to improve our understanding of stellar physics. The detection of mixed modes has indeed made it possible to peer into the cores of red giants. This is currently bringing novel constraints on several physical processes in stellar interiors that remain poorly modeled but are known to play an important role in stellar evolution, such as the mixing of chemical elements beyond the boundaries of convective regions, or the way angular momentum is transported inside stars. We here give an overview of what the seismology of red giants is teaching us about such processes.

*Speaker

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Red Giant Asteroseismology in the Gaia Era

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Abstract

Stellar oscillations are powerful tools for understanding the structure and evolution of stars. With the advent of time domain space missions they can now be measured for large samples of evolved cool stars. The combination of this asteroseismic data, astrometry from Gaia, and large spectroscopic surveys is transforming our understanding of stellar populations and stellar physics. In this talk I review the current state of the art in red giant asteroseismology using the APOKASC2 sample: focusing on how well we can measure absolute masses and radii. I will also discuss the powerful combination of asteroseismology and Gaia, providing three examples: testing the parallax zero point in Gaia with asteroseismology, testing asteroseismic scaling relations with Gaia, and tests of the absolute temperature and bolometric correction scales using both.

*Speaker

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New pulsation physics from unusual red giant stars?

Dennis Stello^{*†1}

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Abstract

Recent analysis of Kepler data has revealed a 'new type' of oscillating red giants. They were found among a sample of distant stars thought to be representative of the galactic halo. Their power spectra show unusually broad features akin F-type main sequence stars with very short mode lifetime. Are these stars the 'bloody F-stars' of red giants with short mode lifetimes, or do they display long lived modes but with a more complex frequency pattern compared to the red giants we have known until now?

In this talk I will present our seismic data analysis, modeling and spectroscopic follow-up from Keck in an attempt to understand what kind of stars these are and why they show such unusual power spectra.

*Speaker

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Discontinuities in the core of red giant stars: effect on the mixed-mode pattern and how to measure it

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Abstract

The *Kepler* mission has provided seismic data of unprecedented quality which brought new ways to precisely measure the stellar seismic parameters, particularly for solar-like pulsators. Among them, red giant stars exhibit complex spectra showing pressure modes as well as mixed modes. The latter are a result of waves that behave as pressure waves in the star envelope and gravity waves in their core allowing to probe it. One of the informations we can extract concern the structural discontinuities present in the core of the star: the so-called glitches. During the talk, we will investigate the influence of these glitches on the mixed-mode frequencies. Then, we will present a method which allows their characterization by the precise measurement of the mixed-mode frequencies and apply it on several stars. Finally, the implications of the results on the physical processes producing the discontinuities will be developed.

*Speaker

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Asymptotic view of oscillations of red giant stars

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Abstract

Since the pioneering works by Shibahashi (1979) and Tassoul (1980), asymptotic analysis has been of fundamental use in the study of stellar oscillations. This is a theoretical framework to understand the physics of the oscillations under the assumption that the wavelength of the constituent waves are much shorter than the scale height of the background structure. The recent detection of solar-like oscillations in red giant stars provides another case for the application of the framework. In this presentation, we describe how the asymptotic analysis can be extended to the case of the red giant oscillations in order to understand their unique characteristics and the internal structure of the stars. The analysis turns out to be useful to extract detailed information from the complicated frequency spectra, which have been obtained by the recent space missions.

*Speaker

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Oscillation properties of High Luminosity Red Giants

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Abstract

Kepler and OGLE observations show a continuity in the behavior of the oscillation spectra from the bottom of the first red giant branch until the highest luminosity red giant stages. The cool-high luminosity region of the HRD is occupied by low mass stars before the He-flash, and stars post central-He burning phase, that is EAGB and TP-AGB stars. These long period variables (LPV) have been classically considered as radial pulsators, however, the fine structure in the P-L diagram of red variables in the Magellanic Clouds also indicates the presence of non-radial oscillations. In this contribution we show the theoretical predictions for the properties of oscillation spectra (radial and non-radial) of high luminosity red giants. We simulate the seismic properties of a complex stellar population, such as that of SMC and LMC, and, by comparison with OGLE observations of MCs, we characterise the different sequences in their P-L diagram.

*Speaker

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The contribution of asteroseismology to a better understanding of helium core burning sdB stars

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Abstract

SdB stars are evolved compact objects of about 0.47 Ms burning helium in their core. Some develop nonradial oscillations driven by a kappa effect powered by the accumulation of iron and nickel in their envelope through the selective action of radiative levitation. They come into two main flavors that show p-mode oscillations on a timescale of minutes (the V361 Hya class) or g-modes with periods of 1-4 hours (the V1093 Her class). These pulsations have been particularly propitious to the development of detailed asteroseismic investigations of the internal properties and fundamental parameters of these stars. Here, I review the contribution of asteroseismology to a better understanding of sdB stars, regarding in particular their link to stellar evolution. I also discuss their potential to constrain important processes that occur in the deep interior of helium core burning stars and that ultimately shape the structure of white dwarfs.

*Speaker

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PB8783 - a trailblazer for hot subdwarf asteroseismology in globular clusters?

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Abstract

Pulsating hot subdwarf stars are one of the showcases of asteroseismology. Thanks to the combination of rich pulsation spectra and state-of-the-art modelling tools it is possible to tightly constrain fundamental parameters such as the stellar mass. One of the remaining mysteries is the marked difference between the hot subdwarf (sdB and sdO) population observed in the Galactic field and in globular clusters (GCs). The few hot subdwarf pulsators so far discovered in GCs do not appear to have clear counterparts among the field population. Recently, it was suggested that PB8783, one of the very first sdB pulsators discovered in 1997, may in fact be an unrecognised hot sdO star with very similar properties to the GC pulsators. We present here new, high-resolution UVES spectroscopy of PB8783 as well as an asteroseismic analysis of the pulsator and answer the question: ordinary sdB or first field counterpart to the GC pulsators?

*Speaker

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Oscillation mode variability in pulsating hot B subdwarfs and white dwarfs

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Abstract

Kepler provides the unique opportunity to characterize the long-term behaviours of oscillation modes in pulsating stars. We find that many modes in evolved compact pulsators show clear amplitude and/or frequency variations in diversity patterns. Such behaviors are typical signatures of nonlinear interactions between coupled resonant modes. Our results suggest that oscillation modes having diverse modulation patterns is a common phenomenon in pulsating sdB and WD stars. This finding should motivate a more precise stellar oscillation theory to be developed, involving in particular weak nonlinear effects. It also raises a warning for long-term projects aiming at measuring the rate of pulsation mode period change caused by stellar evolution or the presence of stellar (planetary) companions. Similar phenomena are presumably present in many types of pulsating stars across the HR diagram with the Kepler, K2 and TESS data.

*Speaker

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Stellar Autopsies from White Dwarf Pulsations

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Abstract

As the endpoints of all low-mass stars, white dwarfs serve as a representative sample for the future of stars like our Sun, as well as binary and even planetary systems. Precision measurements of these stellar fossils can help us calibrate how we expect stars to evolve. We are nearing the end of a multi-year effort to find and monitor thousands of evolved stars using the second-life of the Kepler space telescope, K2. The unprecedented light curves we have collected are revolutionizing our understanding of white dwarf rotation rates, providing fresh insight into how and when stars lose most of their angular momentum. I will review our biggest insights, the bright future with TESS, and a surprising discovery enabled by Kepler along the way.

*Speaker

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Driving Pulsation Modes in Hot DA White Dwarfs

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Abstract

The existence of g-mode instabilities in hot (Teff of order 30,000 K) H-atmosphere (DA) white dwarfs has been predicted by Hiromoto many years ago. Observational evidence has since been gathered showing that at least one hot DA star (and possibly two more) indeed undergoes such pulsations. These rare hot DAV's should not be confused with the classical ZZ Ceti pulsators, also DA white dwarfs, with much lower effective temperatures (of order 12,000 K). The latter exhibit low-degree g-mode pulsations, which are driven by convective driving associated with the partial recombination of H at these temperatures. In this presentation, I revisit Hiromoto's idea that hot DAV white dwarfs are basically pulsating DB stars (the V777 Her variables found in the range from 31,000 K to 24,000 K) "deguised" as DA white dwarfs through the presence of a very thin H outer layer on top of a He mantle where the "action" in terms of driving/damping goes on.

*Speaker

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The mystery of GW Vir instability strip in the light of new observations of PG 1159 stars

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Abstract

The first of the three classical pulsational instability strips of white dwarf pulsators, the GW Vir strip, is populated by stars of PG 1159 and [WCE] spectral types. In contrast to the purity of the DAV and DBV instability strips, only about half of the stars in the GW Vir domain pulsate. This has been explained by a complex combination of atmospheric chemical abundances, and interactions of stellar winds and diffusion. Another intriguing theoretical prediction is that pulsations excited by the epsilon mechanism may be present in some GW Vir stars. To evaluate these theories, we carried out a survey for pulsations among several dozens PG 1159 stars using high-quality, high-speed photometric observations. I will present the results of our survey, and discuss their implications.

*Speaker

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Non-luminous sources of cooling in pulsating white dwarfs

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Abstract

White dwarfs cool through several processes, including the emission of weakly interacting particles such as neutrinos. By their very nature, weakly interacting particles are difficult to observe. In pulsating white dwarfs, however, the effect they have on the cooling rate translates into an observable change in the pulsation periods. Namely, the periods of some modes vary on long time scales that are consistent with a rate of change due to cooling. Such changes in periods have been measured and have allowed us to place limits on the cooling of white dwarfs due to weakly interacting particles. We discuss the technique and present results from such studies, including an update on the mass determination of hypothetical weakly interacting particles called axions, candidate dark matter particles.

*Speaker

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Session 3

STELLAR PHYSICS: MODELLING AND THEORY

Current problems in stellar evolution

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Abstract

The theory of stellar evolution plays a central role in astrophysics as stellar models are used to infer properties for Galactic and Extragalactic stellar populations as well as exoplanetary systems. However, despite decades of experience, stellar models still face major issues linked to transport processes of chemicals and angular momentum. This review will focus on some of the processes responsible for the most sizable uncertainties in stellar models such as for example convection, rotation and mass loss. The presentation will discuss their implementation, their impact on theoretical predictions and how various observational constraints can help us gain insight on the physics inside stars and face the current challenges of the theory of stellar evolution.

*Speaker

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Coupling interior and atmospheric models

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Abstract

When constructing stellar structure models one needs to formulate appropriate inner and outer boundary conditions. For formulating the outer boundary condition, results stemming from model atmospheres are used at various levels of sophistication. I will discuss the basic procedures and involved issues when applying 1D and hydrodynamical 3D model atmospheres. Primarily asteroseismology has driven the developments towards so called patched models where the whole outer structure of an atmospheric model is coupled to an inner stellar structure model, providing overall models of perhaps highest physical fidelity.

*Speaker

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Understanding mixing processes through asteroseismology

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Abstract

It is well established that mixing processes have a significant impact on the evolution and structure of any type of star. However, especially in the context of the outer stellar layers many models still neglect their impact. This is partly because the implementation of more realistic convection, atomic diffusion and rotation treatment is very complex but also because their exact contributions is not well understood. The only way to directly measure this is to study pulsating stars, using asteroseismology. In this talk I will give an overview over how asteroseismology can be used to study mixing processes, and I will show the latest results.

*Speaker

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Constraints on Convection and Overshoot

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Abstract

Convection is one of the major mixing processes in stars, and is crucial for understanding their structure and evolution. One area of uncertainty is the amount of convective mixing that extends beyond the convective boundary, described by the convective overshoot parameter. This extra mixing effectively extends the convective region, changing the properties of the star. However, these processes occur in the deep interior of the star, and cannot be observed directly. For this reason, the extent of the overshoot region is highly uncertain, and whether and how it changes with the stellar properties is unknown. The overshoot parameter can be determined using its effects on the pulsation frequencies of a star, but the detailed modelling required has only been done for a few stars. In this talk, I will summarize how we determine convective overshoot in stars, and what this tells us about the behaviour of the convective overshoot parameter.

*Speaker

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Calibration of the mixing length of the MLT and FST models using 3D hydrodynamical models

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Abstract

The high-quality data of solar-like oscillations by CoRoT and Kepler would enable us to precisely determine stellar characteristics. To make the best of such data, we need stellar models with precise near-surface structure, which significantly impacts on solar-like oscillation frequencies. The mixing length of convection models is a key factor for the near-surface structure. We calibrated values of the mixing length parameters of the classical mixing length theory (MLT) and the full spectrum turbulence (FST) model based on 3D CO5BOLD models. The parameter values are found to vary substantially with effective temperature and surface gravity. It implies that the calibrated parameter values should be implemented into evolution codes instead of fixing the parameter values during the evolution. collaborators: H.-G. Ludwig, M.-A. Dupret, R. Samadi, K. Belkacem, E. Caffau, J. Montalbán, M.-J. Goupil

*Speaker

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Anisotropic shear-driven turbulent transport in stellar radiative zones

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Abstract

Helio- and asteroseismology have allowed us to probe the internal rotation of the Sun and of an increasing number of distant stars. This revealed that an efficient transport of angular momentum is in action in the whole Hertzsprung-Russel diagram with resulting weak differential rotations that current rotating stellar evolution models fail to reproduce. In this context, we developed a new theoretical model of horizontal turbulent transport due to the shear instability that includes for the first time the combined effects of rotation, stable stratification, and radial shear. Compared to previous prescriptions, this improved physical model predicts a possible strong enhancement of the transport of angular momentum by the meridional circulation for solar-type and subgiant stars. However, because of the self-regulation of this mechanism, the differential rotation is still too large and another process should be in action.

^{*}Speaker

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What have we learnt about B-type stars from their pulsations?

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Abstract

High-precision space observations have revolutionized our knowledge about many pulsators. It appeared that in most (if not all) B-type pulsating stars both pressure (p) and gravity (g) modes are observed, i.e., they are hybrid pulsators of beta Cep/SPB or SPB/beta Cep type. This discovery has opened up a possibility of getting more stringent constraints on parameters of the model and theory because a simultaneous excitation of p and g modes offers probing stellar regions sensitive to various physical processes. On the other hand, the presence of high order g-modes in beta Cep stars and p modes in SPB stars is a challenging fact waiting for explanation because these modes are stable in all standard opacity models. In this talk, we will present the main results obtained from seismic studies of B-type pulsators. In particular, we will discuss seismic constraints obtained for convective overshooting, internal rotation and stellar opacities.

*Speaker

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On the photometric detection of internal gravity waves in massive stars.

Bowman Dominic*^{†1}, Conny Aerts¹, Philipp Edelmann², Cole Johnston¹, May Gade Pedersen¹, Tamara Rogers², Sergio Simón-Díaz³, Timothy Van Reeth⁴, Bram Buysschaert¹, and Andrew Tkachenko¹

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⁴University of Sydney – Sydney Institute for Astronomy (SIfA), School of Physics, The University of Sydney, NSW 2006, Australia

Abstract

Understanding the physics of massive stars is an important goal for astronomy as these stars have the largest uncertainties in stellar evolution theory. Without observational constraints of internal rotation and mixing processes, which strongly influence stellar lifetimes, the accuracy of stellar models is limited. Specifically, Internal Gravity Waves (IGWs) are known to be efficient at transporting angular momentum and produce stochastic low-frequency variability near the stellar surface, but IGWs have remained largely undetected in observations. In this talk, we present the results from our recent search for IGWs in space photometry of O, B, A and F stars, and confront them with predictions from 3D hydrodynamical simulations of IGWs. Thus, we place constraints on the surface amplitudes and frequencies of IGWs in massive stars for a wide range in mass on the HR diagram.

*Speaker

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Atomic diffusion in G and F type stars and its impact on the asteroseismic determinations of stellar parameters

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Abstract

Atomic diffusion, including the effect of radiative accelerations on individual elements, leads to variations of the chemical composition inside the stars as well as the surface abundances evolution. Indeed the accumulation in specific layers of the elements, which are the main contributors of the local opacity, modifies the internal stellar structure and surface abundances. Here we show that the variations of the chemical composition induced by atomic diffusion in G and F type stars can have significant impact on their structure, stellar parameters and seismic properties. We will also discuss the effect of the coupling between rotation and atomic diffusion for such stars. These processes need to be taken into account in stellar evolution models as the observations are more and more precise, especially in the context of the space missions TESS and PLATO. We will illustrate these issues with some case studies.

*Speaker

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Opacity calculations for stellar astrophysics

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Abstract

I review the role of radiative opacity in asteroseismology, as well as recent progress and remaining challenges in its calculation, highlighting the modeling difficulties, such as the accounting for myriads of lines or plasma density effects. A particular attention is paid to iron, due to its role in the understanding of Beta-Cephei- and SPB-type stars, as well as of the Sun. The importance of laboratory experiments to check the quality of the computed data is underlined and some X-ray and XUV laser and Z-pinch photo-absorption measured spectra are compared with predictions of the fine-structure opacity code SCO-RCG. An analysis of the recent and unexplained iron opacity measurements performed on the Z machine in conditions close to the ones of the base of the convective zone of the Sun is presented and several theoretical aspects are discussed, such as collisional excitation, auto-ionization, multi-photon processes or line broadening.

*Speaker

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The effect of atomic diffusion on gravity modes of young stars with a convective core

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Abstract

Asteroseismology provides the best tool to probe stellar interiors. Based on high-precision long-term space photometry, recent studies have shown that current stellar models are not adequate in describing element and angular momentum transport. In this talk we present the effects of including atomic diffusion with and without radiative levitation in stellar evolution and pulsation computations. Furthermore, we compare the difference in frequencies caused by diffusion with those from other uncertain input physics. Our results show that atomic diffusion should not be neglected in forward modelling based on gravity modes of intermediate-mass stars, as it affects frequencies and the morphology of period spacing patterns. Understanding the full impact of atomic diffusion on pulsation modes serves as a future step towards improved modelling of main sequence stars with masses between 1.4 and 8 solar masses observed by *Kepler*.

*Speaker

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Pulsating Stars in Binaries

Simon Murphy*^{†1}

¹Sydney Institute for Astronomy (SIfA) – University of Sydney, NSW 2006, Australia

Abstract

Binaries anchor many of the fundamental relations we rely upon in our analyses. Masses and radii are rarely constrained better than when measured via orbital dynamics and eclipse depths. Pulsating binaries have so much to offer! They are clocks, moving in space, that encode orbital motion in the Doppler shifted pulsation frequencies. They offer twice the opportunity to obtain an asteroseismic age, which is then applicable to both stars. They enable comparative asteroseismology - the study of two stars by their pulsation properties, whose only fundamental differences are the mass and rotation rates with which they were born. And when their orbits are eccentric, oscillations can be excited tidally, informing our knowledge of tidal dissipation and resonant frequency locking. I will present an overview of these themes in light of both observational and theoretical developments recently made possible by space-based photometry.

*Speaker

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Post-common-envelope binary stars: Radiative levitation and blue large-amplitude pulsators

Conor Byrne^{*†1,2} and Simon Jeffery^{2,1}

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²Armagh Observatory and Planetarium (AOP) – College Hill, Armagh BT61 9DG, United Kingdom

Abstract

Common envelope (CE) evolution is a phase of close binary evolution which may lead to the formation of exotic stellar objects, such as hot subdwarf stars. The effects of atomic diffusion, particularly radiative levitation, have been shown to play a significant role in the post-CE phase of evolution. Following the recent discovery of blue large-amplitude pulsators (BLAPs), further models of post-red giant branch stars that have undergone a CE ejection were constructed. Here we present the results of pulsation analysis of post-CE models of 0.3 and 0.46 solar mass stars that subsequently become a low mass white dwarf and a hot subdwarf respectively. The effect that atomic diffusion has on pulsations in these models was examined. It is found that the inclusion of radiative levitation allows sufficient enhancement of heavy metals to produce opacity-driven fundamental mode pulsations with periods comparable to those observed in BLAPs

*Speaker

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Tidal Asteroseismology of Heartbeat Binary Stars

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Abstract

We perform a global variability study of about 40 heartbeat stars, a class of eccentric binaries whose light curves resemble a cardiogram. We examine the power spectra of light curve residuals after removing the binary light curve, searching for signatures of rotation and oscillations. Special attention is given to systems that show Tidally Excited Oscillations (TEOs). We show that both pulsation amplitude and phase can be utilized to identify the pulsation mode. In particular, pulsation phases (w.r.t the periastron passage) are extracted to identify the azimuthal number m . To study non-linear mode coupling, we also search for tidally excited non-orbital-harmonic frequencies. For most of the systems, we also present the analysis of spectra obtained from Keck HIRES.

*Speaker

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Damping rates and frequency corrections of Kepler LEGACY stars

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Abstract

We model damping rates and modal frequency corrections for twelve Kepler LEGACY stars. The stability calculations adopt the nonlocal, time-dependent convection model by Gough (1977), implemented consistently in both the stellar equilibrium modelling and in the nonadiabatic pulsation calculations. The global stellar parameters and depths of surface convection zones are obtained from frequency-calibrated ASTEC evolution calculations and the nonlocal convection parameters are calibrated against a grid of 3D hydrodynamical simulations and LEGACY linewidth measurements .

We find good agreement between linewidth data and damping rates and, at the same time, also between the 3D and 1D results of turbulent pressure profiles and anisotropies of the turbulent velocity field. The absolute modal frequency corrections, relative to a standard adiabatic pulsation calculation, increase with surface temperature and surface gravity.

*Speaker

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Slowing the Spins of Stellar Cores

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Abstract

Asteroseismic measurements of red giant stars reveal that their cores rotate much faster than their surfaces, but much slower than theoretically predicted, indicating an unidentified source of AM transport operates in their radiative cores. I examine the magnetic Tayler instability, finding that the instability is limited by the shear energy available to drive it, and the ensuing turbulent AM transport does not depend on the operation of a dynamo loop. AM transport is more efficient than prior predictions, and I provide prescriptions for the effective AM diffusivity. For a reasonable turbulent saturation parameter $\alpha=0.03$, these models largely reproduce a) the nearly rigid rotation of the Sun and main sequence stars, b) the core rotation rates of low-mass red giants during hydrogen shell and helium burning, and c) the rotation rates of white dwarfs.

*Speaker

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Session 4

TRANSDISCIPLINARITY: IMPORTANCE OF PRECISE STELLAR KNOWLEDGE

On-going ground-based and space projects and perspectives

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United Kingdom

Abstract

In this invited talk I will review the range of currently available ground- and space-based data that are relevant to asteroseismic studies of stars. I will also discuss future programmes, and consider the science potential offered by different combinations of existing and future data.

*Speaker

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Synergy between asteroseismology and exoplanet science: an outlook

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Abstract

Over the past decade, space-based asteroseismology has played an important role in the characterization of exoplanet-host stars and their planetary systems. The future looks even brighter, with space missions such as TESS, CHEOPS and PLATO ready to take on this legacy. In this talk, I will start by reviewing current key synergies between asteroseismology and exoplanetary science, such as the precise determination of radii and ages of host stars, the measurement of spin-orbit alignment, and the determination of orbital eccentricity via asterodensity profiling. I will conclude with an outlook on future synergies (e.g., the precise characterization of super-Earths/Neptunes orbiting solar-type stars and the prospect of conducting a populational study of giant planets around evolved stars) and further provide an overview of the asteroseismic yield of exoplanet-host stars expected for the TESS mission.

*Speaker

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Planets and p-mode oscillations of a K-giant, HD 102103

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Abstract

We have been engaged in a long-term radial velocity (RV) planet search program of this kind, using the 10-m Hobby-Eberly Telescope and the 3.6-m Telescopio Nazionale Galileo. So far, our program has discovered over 25 planets and planetary systems around red giants, and it has importantly contributed to our current understanding of the fates of planetary systems orbiting evolving stars.

A serious challenge one has to confront, while using the RV technique to detect planets around giants is that the precision of RV measurements is affected by stellar oscillations. In this presentation, we illustrate this problem with long-term RV measurements of a K-giant, HD 102103. Using the Bayesian inference to model the p-mode oscillations, and the standard, non-linear least squares fitting of an orbital model to the measured RV variations, we parametrize both the stellar oscillations and the planetary orbits.

*Speaker

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Asteroseismology and Galactic archeology

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Abstract

The Milky Way is a complex system, with dynamical and chemical substructures, where several competing processes such as mergers, secular evolution, gas accretion and gas flows take place. To study how such a giant spiral galaxy was formed and evolved, we need to reconstruct the sequence of its main formation events with high temporal resolution. Asteroseismology provides the way forward, allowing to determine precise, potentially accurate ages for tens of thousands of stars in the Galaxy. In this contribution I will review the progress in the field, discussing opportunities and limitations related to the use of seismic data for stellar population studies. I will then highlight how ensemble asteroseismology enables tests of stellar structure and evolution, which are key to improve our ability to determine stellar ages and chemical yields, with wide impact e.g. on population synthesis, integrated colours and thus ages of galaxies.

*Speaker

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Dark matter constraints from the Sun and stars

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Abstract

I will briefly review the current status of the experimental search for, and theoretical research of dark matter. This will be followed by a discussion about the impact of dark matter in stars, with focus on how solar neutrinos, helioseismology and asteroseismology are used to put constraints on the properties of dark matter. Finally, I will discuss about how stars can contribute for the resolution of the dark matter problem.

*Speaker

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POSTERS

First Posters Session

Combining multiple structural inversions to constrain the Solar modelling problem

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Abstract

The Sun is the most studied of stars and a laboratory of fundamental physics. However, the understanding of our star is staid by the solar modelling problem which can stem from various causes. We combine inversions of sound speed, an entropy proxy and the Ledoux discriminant with the position of the base of the convective zone and the photospheric helium abundance to test combinations of ingredients such as equation of state, abundance and opacity tables. We study the potential of the inversions to constrain ad-hoc opacity modifications and additional mixing in the Sun. We show that they provide constraints on these modifications to the ingredients and that the solar problem likely occurs from various sources and using phase shifts with our approach is the next step to take.

^{*}Speaker

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Bolometric corrections and luminosities of roAp stars: preparing to explore the TESS roAp survey

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Abstract

TESS will provide the first systematic space-based search for roAp stars. The increase in the number of known roAp stars, as well as the high-quality of the TESS seismic data will allow for ensemble asteroseismic studies of these pulsators, along with detailed studies of a number of them.

It is important that the new seismic data is complemented by accurate classical data. With this in mind, we will present a new calibration of the bolometric correction (BC) derived specifically for Ap stars, based on the observed spectral energy distributions for the targets of our Ap interferometric program. From the new BC calibration and the GAIA DR2 parallaxes, we derive luminosities for the known roAp stars and compare them to the literature values. We then discuss the impact that the TESS data complemented by accurate classical parameters will have on this field.

*Speaker

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New seismic method exploiting the glitches' information in solar-like pulsators

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Abstract

We present a new asteroseismic method - WhoSGLAd - to provide a comprehensive analysis of oscillations spectra of solar-type stars. We define indicators that are as uncorrelated and as precise as possible thanks to Gram-Schmidt's orthogonalisation process. These indicators provide constraints about the mass, the age, the chemical composition and the undershooting inside of a star. Therefore, the method allows a considerable improvement in the characterisation of solar-like pulsators and is a crucial step to their understanding. Also, the obtention of models of better quality is essential to inverse modeling. Finally, we apply our method to the case of 16CygA.

*Speaker

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Binary Asteroseismic and Isochrone Modelling: Applications to Kepler g-mode Pulsators

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Abstract

Stellar modelling is challenged by the necessary inclusion of several uncalibrated hence parametrized processes, such as convective core overshooting, chemical mixing, rotation, etc. These introduce degeneracies into observable quantities. Typically, techniques that calibrate these processes are restricted to either asteroseismology or binary modelling. Despite extensive discussion of their complementarity, the simultaneous application of these two techniques remains limited. Here, we discuss such applications and results of combined asteroseismic binary modelling to Slowly Pulsating B Stars in binaries observed with Kepler. We focus on the dependence of their mass and evolutionary stage on the internal processes, and discuss deviations compared to the single star case.

^{*}Speaker

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The Nainital-Cape Survey-V: The Kepler View

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Abstract

A dedicated survey programme "The Nainital-Cape Survey" was initiated about two decades ago aiming to search for the low-amplitude pulsational variabilities in a well-defined set of Ap and Am stars. Here, we present the light curves, frequency spectra and derived various astrophysical parameters of 5 additional Ap stars observed from Sutherland site of SAAO. We search for photometric variability in all the observed stars in Kepler and found that time-series data of only 7 stars are available in a K2 archive. Our analysis shows that none of 5 samples observed from Sutherland exhibit any photometric variability, hence can be classified as null results. We conclude that if the CP stars are subjected for photometric variability through high-precision data, then most of them would turn out to be photometric variables where the variability can be used as a key tool to probe the interior and dynamics of the stellar interior using asteroseismology.

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†Speaker

Pulsation and Rotation of the EL CVn-type Eclipsing Binary J0247-25

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Abstract

EL CVn-type eclipsing binaries are composed of a massive A-type main-sequence primary star and a hotter B-type secondary one. We monitored one of these rare and interesting objects, J0247-25, with the KMTNet 1.6m telescopes at two sites of SAAO and SSO. Using the photometric data obtained for a total of 23 nights, we constructed well-defined eclipsing light curves in B, V-bands and derived absolute parameters of each binary component. After subtracting model eclipsing curves from the data, we detected seven frequencies ranging from 33 to 53 c/d and classified them to be Delta Sct-type pulsations originated from the A-type primary component. Pulsation modes of these frequencies were identified on the basis of frequency distribution, rotation effect, and mode visibility. The rotation period of the primary star, derived from rotational m-mode splitting, turned out to be 13% slower than synchronization with the binary orbital motion.

*Speaker

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Modeling of center-to-limb observable for time-distance helioseismology.

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Abstract

Time-distance analysis is a powerful method of helioseismology to study convective or large-scale flows in the solar subsurface. The main quantities in the analysis are travel time of wave packets, which are measured between points on the solar surface. The travel times are subject to systematic errors, which occur because of a nontrivial relationship between wave displacement and helioseismic intensity. In this study, we solve the radiative transfer equation in a solar atmosphere considering displacements caused by acoustic oscillations. The displacements are obtained by solving a vectorial wave equation in a solar model that includes an atmosphere. These displacements provoke perturbations in atmospheric thermodynamical quantities, which perturb opacity and intensities. We investigate the contribution of such perturbations on an emergent intensity and estimate their impact on helioseismic travel time measurements.

*Speaker

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Radial velocity monitoring of candidate hybrid A- and F-type stars from the Kepler mission

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Abstract

An ensemble of 50 candidate hybrid A/F-type stars from the *Kepler* mission was monitored during four years with the *HERMES* spectrograph attached to the Mercator telescope. From this survey, we obtained new radial velocities, new or improved atmospheric properties (T_{eff} , $\log g$, $v \sin i$), and classified all our targets in terms of evidence for multiplicity, pulsation and/or fast rotation. An extension of 40 new candidate hybrid A- and F-type stars from the *Kepler* mission has been recently defined for a second survey to be performed under similar conditions. The new high-resolution spectra will be obtained with various small to medium-sized telescopes. For a number of newly detected stellar systems with good radial velocity coverage, we also computed much improved orbits by combining the radial velocities with the time delays obtained via the monitoring of the pulsation frequencies during the four years of *Kepler* photometry.

*Speaker

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An analysis of three Gamma Dor/ Delta Sct hybrid candidate stars observed by KEPLER

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Abstract

A seismological analysis of the stars KIC 03097912, KIC 04556345 and KIC 04919818 observed with the Kepler satellite is reported. The stars were observed in long cadence mode (exposure time 30 min) during 16 quarters between 2009 and 2013 years. A Fourier analysis of the light curves yielded the detection of +30 oscillation frequencies with a confidence level above 99

*Speaker

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Unveiling new main-sequence solar-like stars observed by K2 using EVEREST time series

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Abstract

The NASA K2 has been observing selected fields near the ecliptic plane since 2014. With only two working reaction wheels, observations can only be done for up to around 85 days towards a given field. However, the spacecraft drifts off equilibrium because of the Solar Wind. As a consequence, every 6 hours it fires up its thrusters to come back to its equilibrium position inducing a regular perturbation in the light curves. Several methods have been developed to mitigate the effect of these drifts. In this poster, we use the EVEREST short-cadence time series to study the acoustic modes stochastically excited in main-sequence stars. Compared to previous published analyses of short cadence stars observed in campaigns one to three (Lund et al. 2016) we were able to measure global seismic parameters for about 50% more stars. We present here the analysis of new light curves and the seismic parameters obtained for the additional stars.

*Speaker

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Influence of metallicity on the surface effect

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Abstract

Modern asteroseismic measurements enable us to probe stellar interiors with high accuracy by comparing observed and modeled frequencies. However, the latter suffers from systematic errors, called surface effect, due to poor 1D modeling of the uppermost layers of stars. Previous works have been done using grids of 3D hydro simulations in order to correct frequency differences, but without considering the effect of metallicity. We computed a grid of patched 1D stellar models in which surface layers are replaced by horizontally averaged 3D atmosphere model. We found that the metallicity, counted for through the mean Rosseland opacity, has a strong impact on the surface effect and cannot be neglected. We give a theoretical justification of frequency differences variations as a function of T_{eff} , $\log g$ and κ . Finally, we provide prescriptions for the fitting parameters of the most commonly used correction laws.

*Speaker

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Evolutionary stage of the massive component of the double-lined eclipsing binary V380 Cyg

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Abstract

The V380 Cygni, a double line eclipsing binary consists of two early B-type stars. The age of this system is about 18 mln years. With a small amount of overshooting from the convective core, the primary is beyond the MS. To catch the primary on the MS, the overshooting of at least α_{ov} of order 0.4 and the metallicity of about $Z=0.02$ are needed. It has not been possible to determine yet if such a high value of core overshooting has a physical meaning or do we observe the star in the overall contraction phase or beyond. V380 Cyg was observed by Kepler and the analysis of the light curve has revealed about 300 frequencies in the range $(0,3.5) \text{ d}^{-1}$. We re-analyse the Kepler observations adding the Q15 - Q17 data and include the analysis of seven-year observations from the SMEI. By comparing the theoretical and observed oscillation spectra we try to get clues which evolutionary stage of the massive component of V380 Cyg is more likely.

*Speaker

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Asteroseismology and multi-mode acoustic tomography of the atmosphere of AlpCir.

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Abstract

We will present the analysis of high-resolution spectroscopic time series of Alp Cir obtained with HARPS. Using high-amplitude spectral lines of rare-earth elements we detected a rich spectrum of acoustic oscillations exhibiting the general spacing of modes of $\Delta\nu = 76.3$ μHz . The echelle-diagram of the spectrum exhibits the modes of different degrees. The multi-mode vertical acoustic tomography of the atmosphere was investigated through the bisector analysis of lines of rare-earth elements that are overabundant in superficial "clouds". These revealed the existence in the atmosphere of multi-mode acoustic standing waves with acoustic nodes and layers pulsating with opposite phase on either side of the node. We will discuss peculiarities and prospects of the multi-mode multi-element vertical acoustic tomography of roAp atmospheres.

*Speaker

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Seismic analysis of HR6902A, a benchmark for scaling relations in the high mass domain

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Abstract

HR 6902 is one of the best studied binary systems of the zeta Aur class. That is, long period eclipsing binaries, that are typically formed by an evolved (giant) primary and a hot dwarf companion, i.e. stars of very different effective temperature but similar luminosity, displaying a composite spectrum. These systems are, in principle, excellent tests of evolutionary and structural stellar models.

The combined analysis of CoRoT photometry and spectroscopic follow-up with HARPS has led to drastically improve the accuracy of the binary orbit and star parameters (by a factor about 10 for the radii). Given the independent determinations of masses and radius, the long orbital period, and the high mass of the primary (about 4Msun), the seismic modeling of this target allows us to test the validity/calibration of the scaling relations in a rarely covered mass/radius domain (and with a binary certainly free from tidal effects).

*Speaker

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K2 Observations of Galactic RRd Stars

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Abstract

We have analysed high-precision photometry of 65 double-mode RR-Lyrae (RRd) stars observed during Campaigns 1-16 of NASA's *Kepler* K2 Mission. Among those we have found several low period ratio variables, belonging either to a group of 'anomalous' RRd stars (Soszynski et al. 2016) or to a separate shorter-period group recently identified by Prudil et al. (2017). The non-radial mode at $P_{(nr)}/P_1$ of order 0.615 has been detected in almost every RRd stars for which precise EAP or Pyke photometric reductions have been performed. In about 80% of these variables at least one subharmonic of the nonradial frequency is also identified. This finding indicates that excitation of the non-radial mode is a common property of the RRd stars. The same non-radial pulsation has also been detected in the RRc stars. We show that properties of this puzzling mode is the same in both groups of RR Lyrae-type pulsators.

*Speaker

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Delta Scuti stars in the Galactic bulge

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Abstract

In the Optical Gravitational Lensing Experiment there are more than nine thousand Delta Scuti stars identified in the Galactic bulge fields. This is the most numerous sample of Delta Scuti stars observed so far. We present the results of the frequency analysis of all stars in this sample. The most interesting objects are stars with two and with three radial modes excited simultaneously, which constitute 24 and 4 percent of the analyzed sample, respectively. Also, we found a few stars which likely pulsate in four radial modes. In the poster we present detailed results and properties of the analyzed Delta Scuti stars.

*Speaker

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Asteroseismic modelling of solar-type stars: internal systematics from input physics and surface correction methods

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Abstract

Asteroseismic forward modelling techniques are being used to determine fundamental properties (e.g. mass, radius, and age) of solar-type stars. The need to take into account all possible sources of error is of paramount importance towards a robust determination of stellar properties. We present a study of 34 solar-type stars for which high signal-to-noise asteroseismic data is available from multi-year *Kepler* photometry. We explore the internal systematics on the stellar properties, that is, associated with the uncertainty in the input physics used to construct the stellar models. In particular, we explore the systematics arising from: (i) the inclusion of the diffusion of helium and heavy elements; and (ii) the uncertainty in solar metallicity mixture. We also assess the systematics arising from (iii) different surface correction methods used in optimisation/fitting procedures.

*Speaker

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Sun-a-star Helioseismology with "Solar-SONG": first results of the summer'18 campaign

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Abstract

The "Solar-SONG" project was funded in 2016 with the objective to complement SONG capabilities with continuous (daily) observations of Sun-as-star by means of an automated solar tracker and high performing solar fibre optical system feeding the slit of the echelle spectrograph. The whole system was successfully implemented in May 2018 and we undertook a 2-month continuous campaign of high-cadence (3 s.) solar observations of the echelle solar spectra (about 12 000 per day) that allowed a high precision RV determination (uncertainty of about 0.75 m/s per point).

In this contribution, the "Solar-SONG" project and the preliminary results of the analysis of the two-month time series (characterization of the spectrum of solar oscillations) will be presented. Further, the capability to also perform simultaneous helioseismology at different solar spectral lines (different depths in the solar atmosphere) will be discussed.

*Speaker

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Improving model selection in asteroseismology with Mahalanobis distances

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Abstract

The improvement of stellar structure and evolution models using asteroseismology relies on determining the best match between the theoretical and observed stellar pulsations. Gravity mode pulsators with convective cores, such as the slowly pulsating B-type stars, are ideal laboratories for studying and constraining convective core sizes and boundary mixing – both of which provide one of the largest uncertainties in the stellar structure and evolution models of high mass stars. The comparison between the models and observed frequencies of these stars has usually been done through a χ^2 evaluation. With this talk we introduce a methodology based on Mahalanobis distances coupled to grids of stellar models, and discuss its implications for model selection and parameter estimations.

*Speaker

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A general description of multi-cavity oscillation modes : from coupling through an evanescent zone to glitches

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Abstract

Analytical resonance conditions for oscillation modes in stars are very helpful to examine their frequency spectra and make the link with their internal properties. In general, modes propagate in several resonant cavities, coupled with each other by intermediate evanescent regions. Moreover, local sharp variations in the stellar structure can perturb the frequency pattern, the so-called glitches. Difficulties then can occur in the interpretation of the data when the frequency spectrum results from different contributions, whether coupling through an evanescent region or glitches. Here we will introduce a general resonance condition that can account for a multitude of resonant cavities and glitches. As an illustration, this new formulation will be used to predict the oscillation frequencies in some peculiar cases. Its potential to disentangle the contribution of each ingredient in spectra will be underlined.

*Speaker

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Periodic modulation of pulsation in Cepheids

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Abstract

Periodic modulation of pulsation was recently discovered in numerous Cepheids observed by the OGLE project. The sample of modulated stars includes tens of fundamental mode and first overtone classical Cepheids and all subgroups of type II Cepheids: BL Her, W Vir and RV Tau stars. I will discuss the observational features of these stars; in particular the common modulation of the mean brightness. In principle, such modulation may influence the use of these stars as standard candles, admittedly at the millimagnitude level only. I will compare the properties of modulation detected in Cepheids, with the properties of modulation commonly detected in RR Lyr stars (the Blazhko effect). I will also review whether mechanisms behind the modulation proposed for RR Lyr stars are also feasible for Cepheids. For fundamental mode classical Cepheids, a possible connection between modulation and the Hertzsprung progression will be discussed.

*Speaker

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The period-luminosity relation for delta Scuti stars using Gaia DR2 parallaxes

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Abstract

We have constructed the period-luminosity relation for 286 delta Scuti stars from the catalogue of Rodriguez et al. (2000) by using the Gaia DR2 parallaxes. We plotted absolute V magnitudes against log(period) and we can distinguish two ridges, with a period ratio near 2. The ridge with longer periods is in agreement with the relation McNamara (2011) fitted to a number of metal-rich delta Scuti stars using the Hipparcos parallaxes, and presumably corresponds to the fundamental radial mode. We also used Gaia DR2 parallaxes and Tycho V magnitudes for the period-luminosity relation of 2299 delta Scutis in the Kepler field. These show a similar distribution, also with two ridges. We discuss the possible explanations.

*Speaker

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Second Posters Session

Asteroseismology of SZ Lyn using very high time resolution photometry in BVR bands.

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Abstract

We report new photometric results based on very high time resolution observations in BVR bands of SZ Lyn. The photometric observations were carried out using the 50 cm CDK reflector at Mount Abu Observatory, India, on six nights. WASP and AAVSO data of SZ Lyn were also considered. The observation was primarily attempted to determine the oscillation frequencies beyond the well established main oscillation frequency of 8.295 c/d. The light curves were analyzed for frequencies from 5 to 100 cd-1 with a frequency step size of the order 10-5 cd-1. 7 frequencies were recovered in the light curves. The amplitudes and phases of the frequencies were also determined for mode identification. The comparison of the theoretical and observational amplitude ratios determined the fundamental frequency, 8.295 cd-1, as $l = 0$ mode. No higher order oscillation modes were found except the 6 harmonics of the fundamental frequency for SZ Lyn.

*Speaker

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Angular momentum transport by internal waves in stellar radiative zones: the effect of rotation and shear

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Abstract

Internal waves propagating in stellar radiative zones can lead to a net and efficient angular momentum transport along the evolution of stars. They thus play a key role in determining the internal rotation profile of these regions, that can be probed by asteroseismology. We will present a new analytical study of their propagation, dissipation and associated transport of angular momentum, focusing on the effect of possibly rapid rotation and strong vertical shears. This is done without making any assumption on their relative strength relative to that of the background stable stratification, which allows to scan the efficiency of the wave-induced transport of angular momentum from the pre-main sequence, during which the restoring forces associated with rotation and stratification can be of the same order of magnitude, to the later stages of evolution, for which stratification tends to dominate over rotation.

*Speaker

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A model of rotating convection in stellar interiors: convective penetration and gravity wave generation

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Abstract

Convective transport processes play a crucial role in stellar evolution and structure. We derive a heuristic convection model for how the magnitude of velocities, superadiabaticity, and characteristic length scale with rotation rate as well as with thermal and viscous diffusivities. The convection model permits an estimate of the depth of convective penetration, namely it establishes a relationship between that depth and the local Rossby number, diffusivity, and pressure scale height. The results for upward and downward penetration have a similar scaling with rotation rate and diffusivities, with the differences in their scaling arising from the changes in the background thermodynamic and gravitational states in a convective core. The magnitude of the energy flux of gravito-inertial waves resulting from convective excitation are assessed, where it decreases with increasing rotation rate for a given wave frequency.

*Speaker

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Additional modes and cycle-to-cycle variations of non-Blazhko RR Lyrae stars

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Abstract

In this presentation I show our study on the Kepler non-Blazhko RR Lyrae sample. We analysed long and short cadence Kepler light curves. We prepared the Fourier spectra, the Fourier amplitude and phase variation functions, the O-C diagrams and their Fourier contents etc.

Our main findings: (1) All stars which are brighter a certain magnitude limit show significant cycle-to-cycle variation. (2) We found additional modes excited permanently at least in one third of the sample and some other stars show temporarily excited additional modes. (3) The presence of the Blazhko effect could in all cases be excluded.

The connection between the extra modes and the cycle-to-cycle variation, although it seems to be obvious, is not evident. Anyway, the characteristics of the phenomena strongly resembles the properties of the resonant and chaotic solutions found in the Florida-Budapest hydrodynamical code.

*Speaker

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STELUM: A Progress Report

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Abstract

We present a summary of our ongoing efforts on STELUM. A short name for tools for STELLar modeling from Universit de Montral. We aim to provide a package with applications for stellar modelization of static/equilibrium models, stellar evolution, pulsations along with utilities like graphic presentations or opacity table computations. Although that the various applications are highly configurable they are specialized for white dwarfs, subdwarfs, main sequence and horizontal branch stars with an emphasis on various mechanisms of particles transport. A description of the current applications is presented here along with some results. A roadmap of the future additions is also provided.

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Calibrating white dwarf asteroseismology

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Abstract

The main goal of looking for variability in stars is the unique opportunity to study their internal structure. Once we have extracted independent modes, it appears to be a simple matter of comparing the period spectrum with those from theoretical model grids.

However, we must account not only for observational uncertainties in period determination, but most importantly for the limitations of the model grids, coming from the uncertainties in the constitutive physics, and of the fitting techniques.

In this presentation, we will discuss results of numerical experiments, using different independently calculated model grids (WDEC, LPCODE-PUL, and MESA) and fitting techniques to fit synthetic stars. The advantage of using synthetic stars is that we know the details of their interior structures so that we can assess how well our models and fitting techniques are able to recover the interior structure, as well as the stellar parameters.

*Speaker

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The two-dimensional internal rotation of KIC11145123

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Abstract

The recent asteroseismic inferences of the internal rotation of main-sequence stars generally agree that the low- and intermediate-mass stars rotate almost uniformly regardless of their rotation periods [e.g. Aerts et al. (2017)]. In this study, we would like to present results of estimation of the two-dimensional internal rotation of KIC11145123, which was once thought to be a main-sequence A-type star and recently has been considered spectroscopically as a blue straggler. Based on the Optimally Localized Averaging method and a four-zone modeling of the internal rotation, we have found that the convective core rotates about 6 times faster than the radiative region above. We have also found that there is a significant latitudinal differential rotation in the outer envelope.

These newly discovered features of the internal rotation of the star will help us understand the complex physical properties of the star.

*Speaker

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Effect of diffusion-induced element accumulation on the opacity inside B stars

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Abstract

Stellar models with homogeneous abundances fail to reproduce the pulsation frequencies of early B-type stars. Their oscillations are excited by kappa-mechanism involving the Fe-peak elements where they are main contributors to the opacity (the "Z-bump") and a ad hoc increase of the opacity in these layers is necessary to match the observations.

We test whether atomic diffusion can induce such an opacity increase through Fe and Ni accumulations in the Z-bump. With models computed using the Toulouse–Geneva Evolution Code, we show that atomic diffusion changes the abundance profiles inside the star, leading to an overabundance of the iron-peak elements in the upper envelope. The opacity may reach the amount required by seismic studies, provided that fingering mixing, which extends the size of the overabundance zone, is taken into account. Mass-loss is also required to evolve the model until the end of the main sequence.

*Speaker

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Spectroscopic observations for RR Lyrae stars listed in TESS

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Abstract

We have done spectroscopic observations of RR Lyrae stars listed in TESS target: SU Dra and SW And. We set $R=30,000$ to acquire $S/N > 70$ for 1800s exposure. BOES is the main device of a 1.8m telescope in BOAO (Bohyunsan Optical Astronomy Observatory). It is a fiber fed spectrograph which has three kinds of fibers; $80\mu\text{m}$ ($R=90,000$), $200\mu\text{m}$ ($R=45,000$), $300\mu\text{m}$ ($R=30,000$). If we use a Iodine cell, the resolution of radial velocity is accurate to 5m/s. We check the metallicity and binary characteristics of SU Dra from the long-term based observations. We also check the limiting magnitude for the faint targets.

*Speaker

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Asteroseismic modelling of sub giants: key to accurate stellar ages

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Abstract

Stellar ages from theoretical models are strongly affected by the uncertainties in the input physics. The mixed modes excited in low-mass subgiants are sensitive to the internal structures and their amplitude are strong for high S/N detections. Modelling individual subgiants hence offers the best chance for precise stellar ages. Modelling of the SONG target μ Herculis, as well as 42 Kepler subgiants, shows that its age is much less dependent than that of MS stars on initial helium, metallicity, and mixing-length. Changing the mixing-length or the initial helium abundance does not change the age systematically. Moreover, changing the metallicity by 0.1 dex changes the age by less than about 10 percent for most stars. Thus the seismic modelling of subgiants can significantly reduce the model dependences and give accurate stellar ages.

*Speaker

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On the temperature gradient in the core overshoot zone of intermediate-mass stars

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Abstract

The mass of the He core at the end of the main sequence is a key quantity for the later stages of evolution. This mass depends on the properties of core overshooting, which can be estimated from gravity (g-)modes. We compare the g-mode signature of penetrative convection based on a fully mixed overshoot region with the one due to diffusive decaying overshooting, in view of the capacity of Kepler data to distinguish between these two descriptions of core overshooting. We also compute g-modes for models with a gradual transition from penetrative to diffusive overshooting, including a smooth change from an adiabatic to radiative temperature gradient in this transition zone. We assess the implications of these overshoot prescriptions for the He-core mass built up along the main sequence.

^{*}Speaker

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Spectroscopic long-term monitoring of RZ Cas

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Abstract

Spectroscopic analysis of eclipsing binaries showing pulsations can be used for very precise determination of stellar and system parameters. Moreover in Algol-type systems we can study the effect of mass-transfer episodes on the pulsation pattern. Yet, determining both components radial velocities (RVs) and spectral disentangling remain major problems. Our new approach of calculating least-squares deconvolved (LSD) line profiles uses separate templates for the components and delivers separated RVs and LSD profiles. So it yields recovered spectra from the LSD profiles and line masks and thus performs spectral disentangling based on single composite spectra. We present first results of the application of the new method to an extended spectroscopic time series of the star RZ Cas, showing varying patterns of low-degree l-modes (RVs) and high-degree l-modes (line profile variations) in active and inactive phases of the system.

*Speaker

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Impact of general differential rotation on axisymmetric gravity waves in rapidly rotating stars

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Abstract

Differential rotation plays a key role in stellar evolution by triggering hydrodynamical instabilities and large-scale motions that induce transport of chemicals and angular momentum and by modifying the propagation and the frequency spectrum of inertial gravity waves. It is thus crucial to investigate its effect on the propagation of gravity waves to build reliable seismic diagnostic tools, especially for fast rotating stars, where perturbative treatments of rotation fail. Generalising a previous work done in the case of uniform rotation, we derived a local dispersion relation for gravity waves in a differentially rotating star, taking the full effect of rotation (both Coriolis and centrifugal accelerations) into account. Then we modelled the propagation of axisymmetric waves as the propagation of rays. This allowed us to efficiently probe the properties of the waves in various regimes of differential rotation.

*Speaker

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The long-term photometric variations associated with the LSPs in red giant variables

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Abstract

We explored the long-term V I and JHKs light curves of a large number of red giant variables with long secondary period (LSP) in the SMC using data from OGLE and long-term near-infrared observations. The origin of the magnitude variations in the LSPs is currently unknown. In this work, we obtained a sample of the stars showing prominent LSP. We derived the time-series of the bolometric luminosities and the effective temperatures for our target stars by combining the OGLE and the near-IR data with the Magellanic Clouds Photometric Survey catalog and the Spitzer SAGE SMC IRAC source catalog. Then we estimated the change of the stellar radii derived from the bolometric luminosities and the effective temperatures. We found that radius variations hardly contribute to the luminosity variations in the sample LSPs. This might indicate that non-radial dipole modes oscillations are responsible for the light variations of the LSPs.

*Speaker

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New Pulsation Models of AGB Stars - Exploiting the Potential of Long-Period Variables

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Abstract

Observed periods and amplitudes of Long-Period Variables (LPVs) have a great potential, that promises to be unfolded by current and upcoming large surveys (GAIA, LSST) and the next generation of ground-based and space telescopes (E-ELT, JWST). In order to exploit the potential of LPVs, a detailed modelling of pulsation must be employed. We present an approach based on the combination of synthetic stellar populations with a detailed grid of pulsation models, including the first ever systematic modelling of carbon-rich LPVs, and its application to the interpretation of their observed properties in the Large Magellanic Cloud. This approach unveils some of the major shortcomings in the predictive power of available models of stellar pulsation in evolved red giant stars.

*Speaker

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A new 0.68-m robotic telescope located in the northern hemisphere - Call for proposals

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Abstract

Horten Videregående Skole, an upper secondary school in Norway, has a long tradition in offering observational astronomy courses for specialized science classes. From the past years we have experienced that by choosing stellar targets and observing program in collaboration with science collegium, the observational data that the students obtain can also be used for scientific purposes. We have now expanded our observational capacity with a 0.68-m robotic telescope in Norway, ready in August 2019, and are now open for proposals.

*Speaker

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Evidence of water accretion in GD362?

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Abstract

GD362 is a helium-rich white dwarf with metals in its atmosphere. This is interpreted as a signature of ongoing (or recent) accretion from a circumstellar disk (also observed as an infrared excess in the spectrum). The star also shows a large amount of hydrogen, the origin of which is still under discussion. Accretion from the interstellar medium was ruled out from observational evidences. Convective mixing of a primordial hydrogen layer was also recently suggested. In this work, we use full evolutionary simulations, including accretion and all relevant physical processes, to show that the convective mixing of a primordial hydrogen layer cannot explain the case of GD362. We conclude that accretion of hydrogen-rich material from water-bearing planetesimals may be the reason for its atmospheric composition.

*Speaker

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Frequency identification and asteroseismic analysis of the red giant KIC 9145955: fundamental parameters and helium core size

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Abstract

The oscillation frequencies of KIC 9145955 include 7 ($l = 0$) modes, 44 ($l = 1$) modes, 7 ($l = 2$) modes, and 3 ($l = 3$) modes. We identify ($l = 0$) modes as p modes and ($l = 2$) modes as p-dominated modes. For ($l = 1$) modes, all of them are identified as mixed modes. The helium core is determined to be ($M_{\text{He}} = 0.210 \pm 0.002 M_{\odot}$) and ($R_{\text{He}} = 0.0307 \pm 0.0002 R_{\odot}$) by fitting mixed modes. We also find that only the acoustic radius τ_{ao} can be precisely determined with the asteroseismic method independently. The value of τ_{ao} is determined to be 0.494 ± 0.001 days. By combining asteroseismic results and spectroscopic observations, we obtain the best-fitting model. The physical parameters of this model are ($M = 1.24 M_{\odot}$, $Z = 0.009$, $\alpha = 2.0$, $T_{\text{eff}} = 5069$ K, $\log g = 3.029$, $R = 5.636 R_{\odot}$, and $L = 18.759 L_{\odot}$).

*Speaker

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